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Institutional Ethnography and Visual Research Methods: An Open-Ended Discussion

This paper aims to open a discussion on the intertwining between Institutional Ethnography (IE) and visual methods in sociology. It does so by analyzing and discussing a number of studies. IE considers visuals (photographs, paintings, sculptures, videos, CDs, etc.) like texts (laws, regulations, reports, translations, articles, pamphlets and so on): these are indispensable elements for exploring text-mediated relations of ruling (Smith 1990). The current *Zeitgeist* (spirit of the age) is characterized by people's increasing use of visuals in their everyday practices that affect doing research and its dissemination. Societal changes have made visual texts more usable, available, widespread and sometimes more persuasive. However, a limited number of IE studies explicitly discuss the utilization of visuals and visual research methods in IE research practices. This is the reason why researchers who use IE could benefit from wider discussion about its intertwining with visuals and visual research methods. The analysis of people's visual and sense-making practices and the utilization of visuals and visual research methods in IE are connected aspects. However, this paper will focus mainly on the latter topic. Therefore, it will illustrate how researchers have to date employed visual data, visual research methods and visual dissemination methods in IE, what the other potential uses in the future are, and the aspects in regard to which the debate remains open.

The paper is organized into three parts. The first consists of an introductory overview of what visual methods are, the societal changes that affect their rise, and their intertwining with IE. The second part presents exemplary IE research studies, which use visuals and visual methods for different purposes and employ different research practices. The paper concludes with an open-ended discussion about the strengths and weaknesses of utilizing visual methods in IE.

Visual Methods, Societal Change and IE

It is useful to begin by considering what visual methods are, then the reason for their importance in our society and finally to consider how visual methods intertwine with some aspects of IE. Although visual methods in sociology involve many different approaches, Van den Scott (2018, p. 720) provides a list useful for understanding what visual methods are. These comprise the following: photo elicitation, photo voice, photography and autophotography, family photos, mental or cognitive mapping, GIS mapping, interviews with video or photography, grounded theory mapping, mapping of social groups, art making and its analysis, study of material culture, graffiti, ethnographic content analysis of visual materials like cartoons, movies, paintings, drawings, photographs, and so on. A wide range of visual methods exists with different degrees of collaboration and involvement of the participants and of the researcher. These methods are usually applied in anthropology, psychology and sociology, in qualitative research and classical ethnography, and they can be profitably transferred to IE and adapted to its ontological framework.

Generally, qualitative researchers utilize visuals in three ways: as *data*, as *tools to gather data*, as *tools to record data*. The first case – visuals as *data* – concerns the situation in which researchers conduct content analysis of visual materials that are already available in the social

world (e.g., advertising images become data to analyze). The second case – visuals as *tools to gather data* – concerns the situation in which researchers use visual methods to elicit data from participants. In this case, visuals may be created by the researcher or by participants or by researchers and participants working together. The classic example of this second case is when researchers gather data from participants by means of photo elicitation. The third situation – visuals as *tools to record data* – regards the case of researchers who use visual methods in order to register data in a more detailed and material form, for example when researchers take photographs with the purpose of enriching fieldnotes and memos and representing the material aspects of the problems that they are studying. A fourth situation should be added: when researchers use visual materials from their fieldwork to present, explain and disseminate findings to an academic public or a broader general audience. In summary, ethnographers can 1) analyze visuals, 2) use visuals in order to gather or generate data, 3) use visuals as means to present findings. These three different ways to employ visuals in IE can be combined to generate hybrid uses, as we will see.

The second aspect to be considered concerns why the visual methods are increasingly applied. This has its roots in the extraordinary social and cultural changes that have occurred in recent decades, most notably the transition from logocentrism to imagocentrism. The term *logocentrism* (Klages, 1929) concerns the conception of words and language as fundamental expressions of everyday reality. Logocentrism can be considered an umbrella term that describes not only the relationship between thought, speech, and writing, but also the centrality of that relationship in everyday life. The term *imagocentrism* was coined to describe a culture in which the image is an epistemological referent. De Sousa Santos (2015) explains that logocentrism is related to social and territorial matrices (space and time), while imagocentrism is based on *mediatrixes* (a media-

driven culture) in which space and time are replaced by velocity and superficiality. In imagocentrism the processes of relation and communication are mainly enacted by images. Even if these *-centrisms* might seem *blob* ontologies, it should be considered that the materiality of digital technologies has redefined “how images operate in society” (Harper, 2016, p. 246), how people think and act, and, consequently, how research can be done. Within sociology, this has generated a progressive affirmation of visual research methods that are considered fundamental for investigating societal and cultural changes in an everyday life, which is increasingly *thick* with images (Mirzoeff, 2009). Visual research was underestimated for a long time (Spencer, 2010), and only at the beginning of the current century did scholars recognize the value of this approach. Pink (2006; 2012) considers that the attention paid to visual methods is due to theoretical changes in social sciences, as well as new attention paid to social practices, to the multisensorial nature of knowledge processes, and to the spatial dimension of everyday life. Van den Scott (2018) observes that the affirmation of visual methods was possible only with the reflexive turn in social sciences, and this affirmation was enhanced by the spread and affordability of digital technologies. According to Van den Scott, visual methods can support public sociology from data collection to the dissemination of findings. Herzog (2020) adopts a similar position: visual research methods are fundamental in a society that is using “visual representation as a primary form of communication” (p. 184).

The third aspect to be considered concerns how visual research methods intertwine with some aspects of IE. First of all, IE responds effectively to the *linguistic turn* in the social sciences, directing attention back to people, their quotidian experiences, their everyday-life materiality, their practices in relation to cultural representations. As Smith and Turner (2014) argue, texts are all material objects that convey a message. A text cannot be separated from the concrete relations

that it coordinates in people's everyday activities. A text can be reproduced many times and its replicability is central. This sensitivity of IE to texts and their social settings enables researchers to work with the materiality of visual texts and discover how this materiality can be linked to discursive dimensions through the lived experience. It follows that IE enables researchers to investigate and demonstrate the translocal ruling relations functions of visual texts, both when visuals are considered as *data* and when they are conceived as *tools to gather and record data*. For example, when visuals are tools to gather data, seeing how images are taken up and acted upon by participants makes the application of visual methods to IE effective in understanding the participants' point of view. Indeed, the sensitivity of IE to materiality, joined to the visual methods, enables researchers to make the participants' standpoint and their everyday work more visible, displayable and understandable in the concrete details.

Furthermore, IE can contribute to the study of visual-mediated practices, for example, by analyzing how people look at images, the role of images in their daily lives, their effects, and the acts of meaning attribution. Visuals activate different sensorial modalities and symbolic mechanisms, and considering these practices and mechanisms is necessary during research. Even if IE can certainly make valuable contributions to the study of these visual-mediated practices, the main focus of this paper is broader.

Above all, a crucial point is the role of visual research methods in enhancing IE's attitude of being a sociology *for* people that promotes social and political activism and that engages in change-making practices with regard to social problems. The explanations of Herzog (2020) about how visual methods can significantly contribute to the study of social problems by integrating visual methods into social problems studies can be applied to the intertwining between visual methods and IE. Herzog argues that visuals yield a better understanding of

aspects of social problems that are too abstract and that can benefit from the materiality of visuals; they are of great help when interpreting social problems; they make it easier to call the public audience's attention to social problems.

A Selection of IE Research Studies with the Focus on Visuals

The following selected IE research studies will be analyzed considering the four main categories of visuals and visual methods utilization (as *data*, as *tools to gather data*, as *tools to record data*, as tools to *disseminate* findings), the distinctive nature of the IE research approach, and Herzog's suggestions about visual methods and social problems' analysis.

Some of these studies utilize visual methods in more than one of the four above-mentioned categories of application. Furthermore, these studies do not exhaust all possible applications of visual research methods in IE, since there are many such research methods.

It is useful to begin with the study by Luken and Vaughan (2006), an example of how visuals can be utilized as *data* in IE. Walby (2005) provides another example of visuals as *data* that activate the text/reader conversation and that can be observed by the researcher in their natural setting.

The study by McCoy (1995) is an example of application of photo-elicitation as a *tool to gather data*, while my study (2018) provides a hybrid use of visuals as data and as tools to gather data.

Finally, my study on the transition from double to single motherhood (2019) and the study by Puddu (2018) are examples of the hybrid use of visuals as tools to gather data and to disseminate findings to an academic public or a broader public outside academia.

Archival Visual Data (Help) to Unpack Institutional Discourses

Luken and Vaughan (2006) use visual texts including historical photographs to explicate the social relations shaping housing and family practices in early 20th century United States. The aim of the study is the exploration of “the processes by which an institutional discourse combining childrearing and housing practices was formulated through the work practices of three state-affiliated organizations between 1900 and 1930” (Luken & Vaughan, 2006, p. 300).

Beginning with the oral histories of older women, the authors analyzed how parents took up the discourse of the Standard American Home (SAH) as a form of housing suitable for raising infants and children elaborated by three state-affiliated organizations. They collected documents on childrearing and housing between 1890 and 1930 from the U.S. National Archives and Research Administration (NARA), the Library of Congress, historical societies and museums in cities where the interviewed women lived as children and parents, and library repositories across the United States. Using historical investigative methods to connect the documents to the local experience of these women, as “texts-in-use”, the authors, for example, collected and examined brochures from The Better Homes in America movement – a campaign started in 1922 at a national level – whose demonstration projects and brochures were in the cities in which the women lived. From these brochures, the authors discovered photographs of houses advertised as a part of the annually sponsored Better Homes Week. The use of two of these photographs by the authors allows us to understand how the SAH discourse operated. These photographs show a home before and after the work of remodeling and decoration. The authors argued that the images, their accompanying texts, the contrast between the two appearances of the home posed by the ordering discursively construct the aspiration of the working class, modeling it by an image of a middle class home. Images and their order of presentation work by argumentatively producing class differences. Through these materials, Luken and Vaughan demonstrated that the

SAH discourse universalized and typified aspects and appearances of the homes and furniture and defined home and home ownership as fundamental goods for the construction of a balanced personality in children.

In this example, historical photographs – produced in standardized and replicable forms –are texts-in-use that contributed materially to organizing the responsibility of parents. Through these photographs and their accompanying texts, the institutional ideological code produces a standardization of visual norms and is able to organize the interviewees’ narratives even decades later. This process of organization of knowledge can be activated not only through photographs but also through other visual texts, like posters, newspaper ads, paintings, as these authors demonstrated in other studies (e.g., Luken & Vaughan, 2005).

In conclusion, in light of the above-mentioned suggestions by Herzog (2020), one observes that in the study by Luken and Vaughan (2006) the materiality of visuals is constitutive of the institutional discourses that they analyzed, so that these visual data cannot be neglected either in the analysis or in the discussion of how some concerted ideological codes affect the everyday practices of people. For this reason, it is essential to include the visual texts in the presentation of the results of these studies.

CCTV Texts as Visual Data to Integrate with Participant Observation

Walby (2005) studied how institutional discourses affect the practices of interpretation of CCTV (closed-circuit television) visual texts performed by the camera operators in control rooms and how these practices give rise to forms of racialized discrimination. CCTV, also known as *video surveillance*, is a television system whereby video cameras are used to transmit a signal to a specific number of monitors in the control room, where operators watch images on the monitors,

write logbooks and reports to send to other control agencies, in order to make a specific place, person or activity secure. Walby conducted unstructured interviews with CCTV operators and observed them in their workplace in three organizations in Victoria, British Columbia.

Visual texts shown by the monitors can be considered as *visual data* observed during Walby's fieldwork. He considered a visual text on the monitor as a *rolling text* (a sequence of events in real time on the monitor) or as an *initiating text* (a sequence of events that can be rewritten and reinterpreted). The rolling text enables operators to catch the act of shoplifting. The initiating text reports the act of the offender to the various institutions involved in the process of surveillance, risk detection and risk communication. The operators interpret stimuli from the rolling visual texts and discriminate between people deemed to be suspicious and not suspicious. They transcribe the visual text into a sequence of written texts, which activate processes (like reports and arrests) at local level and far away in translocal organizations. The video can be freeze-framed, extracting pictures of suspects to send to other stores, or to attorneys and courts to report an incident, becoming "a form of text which is central to the coordination of peoples' activities" (Walby, 2005, p. 191).

Walby observed that initiating visual texts have a *replicable* form because they can be sent to various institutions, to various readers who can differently activate the fragments from video recordings, referring to ruling (written) texts that are different from the ruling text of the camera operators. These visual texts are subject to activation through intertextual circles, passing through different activations and interpretations, also after years. The materiality of the CCTV text, because it is activated by diverse subjects (from the camera operators up to the judges), allows to make visible the involvement of the subject in reproducing institutional discourses. The study's findings show how operators participate in reproducing the dominant institutional

discourse using the CCTV videos. Walby argued that the operators aim to protect the practices of contemporary consumerism from the deviant behavior that they commonly identified in Aboriginal shoppers' activities.

Walby's study is interesting because it shows how an institutional ethnographer can observe the process of activation of visual texts in a workplace (see also Walby, 2006). These visual data can be combined and compared with other data collected through observation, interviews and document analysis.

In conclusion, in regard to Herzog's (2020) suggestions, this study yields, through the materiality of visual data, better understanding of abstract aspects of the social problems generated by so-called surveillance society and it enables interpretation of how institutional discourses affect the everyday practices of surveillance and racialized profiling.

Photo-Elicitation to Make the Text/Reader Conversation Visible

McCoy (1995) examined visual texts embedded in the social situations of their use with the aim to discover how people give meaning to these texts and how the interpretive practices of their activation occur. She argued that the practice of "looking at" and interpreting photographs in daily life is socially organized. McCoy analyzed diverse visual texts; but, for the current analysis, the most interesting part of her work concerns study of the sense-making process related to wedding photographs and the institutional discourses that affect this process.

To study this process, McCoy proposed an innovative method using the materiality of visual texts. She made "the text-reader conversation observable by getting three people together (she was one of the group) to talk about the photographs of the wedding of one of them" (Smith, 2005, p. 106). She did not control the conversation, but she followed its natural development.

She applied a kind of *photo-elicitation* in which photographs belong to the wedding album of one of the participants, and photographs are produced by a professional photographer. Photo-elicitation is a method of research that consists in using photographs (or other visual materials) during an interview or a focus group with the aim of activating a discussion with the participants, gathering data on social processes and practices, and exploring different interpretations and reactions by the participants. The visual materials for the photo-elicitation can be chosen among those collected by the researcher or among those collected or created by the participants.

McCoy analyzed how wedding pictures are activated in the talk and by the relations among the viewer, the picture and the owner. These relations and talk show the ability of actors in reading the photographic album as a record of “real events.” In doing this, they apply the ruling interpretive scheme of the ideal wedding discourse. She (1995) observed that “at a wedding people organize a series of actions that aim at discursive ideals of love, romance, family, and so forth” (p. 187). Images, created on and with the bodies, produce the local realization of the wedding’s discursive forms on the basis of those ideals.

Therefore, the small focus group conducted by McCoy made visible the text/reader conversation as a situated activity in the course of action. This means that the act of interpreting during the text/reader conversation connects the visual text to the situation in which that reading is happening and is embedded. In other words, without the presence of the bride in the group, in her study McCoy would have collected a different interpretation of the visual texts.

In conclusion, even if McCoy’s research study appears not to be related to the field of social problems and visual methods as discussed by Herzog (2020), it provides an example of how IE can investigate, through the materiality of visual texts, how people organize their actions, at what discursive ideals they aim, what kind of local realization of these discursive forms is produced.

This approach makes it possible to analyze social processes in detail, so that it can be utilized for a deeper interpretation of social problems.

Photo-Elicitation to Investigate the Accountability Strategies of Court Experts

A research study that I conducted (Tartari, 2018)¹ on court-appointed psychologists as experts illustrates another possible use of photo-elicitation in IE. I investigated the everyday social practices that regulate and coordinate the work of court experts within the judicial context of child custody evaluation from their standpoint, and the strategies that these professionals use to show their responsibility and accountability during these evaluations. I applied a hybrid visual method: I used photograms from previously videorecorded sessions as *visual data* in my autoethnography and as *tools for photo-elicitation* in interviews and focus groups with the participants. The photograms were extracted from a corpus of videorecorded sessions from my professional work, as, for about 20 years, I had worked as a court expert in Italy in the area of psychological assessment of parental responsibilities in order to help courts to decide child custody arrangements.

The research study began with a visual auto-ethnography, where I used visuals as data; then, in a second phase, I conducted interviews and a focus group with court-appointed experts, where I used visual data for a photo-elicitation.

The first phase of the study, the visual auto-ethnography, provided better identification of the research question: that is, how the everyday practices of the experts were textually mediated and shaped by the discourses on responsibility and accountability during psychological assessment of the parents. I analyzed the last ten court-appointed evaluations that I had conducted before leaving my professional job for my academic career. They consisted of ten written reports and of

videorecorded meetings I had with parents and children. On analyzing the videorecorded sessions, I found that the discourses about accountability and responsibility propounded by the judicial system and the professional community induced me increasingly to express my responsibility and reliability in different ways, both verbally and visually, during the process of evaluation. My work was ruled by various texts (code of conduct, guidelines for psycho-forensic evaluation, family law) and by the interpretations that parents, lawyers and (private experts) colleagues made of these texts. Since the autoethnography did not yield sufficient findings, I extended my study to psychologists who were used to working as court-appointed experts and as private experts for parents (in Italy, the legal procedure for the court-appointed expert's evaluation prescribes that each parent may be accompanied by a private expert – a psychologist of their choice – during all sessions of the evaluation).

In this second stage of the research, I conducted a focus group with three experts (as in McCoy, 1995) and some in-depth interviews (because many experts refused to discuss the topic of responsibilities and professional practices in a group with other colleagues). The interview and the focus group followed the same design: a first part with open-ended questions about the procedures that the participants applied to be accountable in the most recent evaluations they had conducted for courts; and a second part concerning the discussion of the images extracted from my work. In this second part, I used a show-and-tell procedure. I selected participants to include a variety of professional experiences, particularly experts with different psychological approaches to the evaluation of parents. Informed consent was provided by the participants and for the data I reused from my professional practice. In addition, I applied a masking technique so that parents and children were not recognizable in the images.

Regarding the selection of the images, I freeze-framed the videorecordings pertaining to the last ten evaluations that I had conducted for courts, extracting some pictures. I selected images that represented practices related to professionals' accountability and responsibility in different phases of the evaluation. For example, I selected images where the setting between the consultant/s and me showed details about how the expert used audio and videorecording, took notes, and discussed these procedures with the parents.

The first image shows me at the desk with a child during a meeting and the technological devices that I used. The second image shows me at the one-way mirror while I am explaining to a father and his daughter the role of the mirror and the presence of other colleagues behind the mirror.

The third image shows me with a parent and his son while I am explaining to them the role of the room with CCTV and of the colleagues in that room. The fourth image shows a technical error concerning operation of the CCTV in the other room resulting in the loss of many minutes of the recording. When I presented the images to participants, I explained to them that the images came from my professional practice and that we could discuss them together. I told them that at the start of the research I had worked on my personal experience, trying to reflect critically about it. I presented the images one at a time, describing each of them briefly.

During the first part of the interview and focus group, the participants provided more off-topic accounts, focusing the narratives mainly on the qualities of the relationship between parents and children, rather than on their practices and strategies concerning accountability and responsibility. However, the photo-elicitation was more fruitful since the second part of interviews and focus groups allowed the experts to discuss, in detailed terms, *disjunctures* between their practices and the institutional discourses. Through the photos, experts were able to focus better on changes in their own practices, differences between their practices and those of

other colleagues, and on how discourses from the legal/judicial field and from the psychologists' professional community affect the need to show and perform responsibility and accountability through specific practices.

The findings of the study can be summarized into two issues. The first is a disjuncture between the discourses from the legal and the psychological fields: the former indicates some practices as accountable and responsible practices, but the latter – in particular the clinical psychology discourse – does not consider some of these practices as responsible. For example, commenting on the first image, an expert considered that audio and videorecording pertain to the legal field that needs evidences and proofs, but not pertinent to the field of psychology. She explained that the use of devices compromises the relationship of trust between parents and experts, which is a kind of relationship defined by the field of the clinical psychology profession and not by the field of other professions involved.

Second, the discourses from clinical psychology failed to promote in the experts a sense of awareness about accountable and responsible practices. Since these discourses maintain the focus on the trust relationship between expert and client (adult or minor), they failed in making the experts aware of the need to keep the focus on the entire process of evaluation, on the institutions involved, and on the projection of the effects of their practices into the future. In other words, participants emphasized that experts have different degrees of *awareness* about the issue of the subsequent *potential* reactivation of the (written or visual) texts collected during the evaluations. When this awareness is present to a large extent, it affects how experts collect data during the evaluation. Because they know that at a different level of the process and in different institutions, other people with similar or different roles can watch their videos or read their reports, they enhance and underline certain kinds of practices. Some participants commented that the more

aware an expert is of the subsequent reactivations of the text, the more s/he acts accordingly in order to anticipate some consequences of this. They commented that this awareness had made necessary, over the years, an increasing “rigidity” of their practices. Such awareness was ruled by the ideals of accountability and responsibility that come from the legal professions. The images that I selected, in their opinion, reflected this rigidity very well.

In conclusion, it is to be observed that in this study visuals are used in a hybrid way: *as data* in the autoethnography and then as *tools to gather data* by the photo-elicitation in the interviews and focus group. In regard to Herzog’s suggestions (2020), this study highlights how visuals can be used to improve the understanding of abstract aspects related to responsibility and accountability as increasingly perceived as problems in professional practices. Visuals contributed also to improving the interpretation of such practices and the social processes related to them.

Using Visuals to Disseminate Findings and Promote Social Justice

Visuals can be utilized for dissemination purposes to an academic or a broader public outside academia. Explaining how people act and how institutions work can become more ethnographically accessible to a broader public if visuals are used. This is the case of an IE project which I am currently conducting (Tartari, 2019) and of a study conducted by Puddu (2018).

My ongoing study² focuses on single mothers’ everyday strategies and social practices to claim inclusion and to negotiate – or not negotiate – the dominant definition of family and parenthood proposed by institutions and professionals and the less legitimated definitions of single parents and their families. In particular, the analysis considers the transition from double parenthood to

single motherhood, paying attention to the period of judicial evaluation for child custody and judicial decisions in regard to allowances and other obligations. The research conducted for the study collects data in Belgium, Italy, Spain, and in the UK through discursive interviews with single mothers, judicial professionals and gender issues activists, participant observations, and photo-voice sessions involving mothers and professionals. Interviews and photo-voice sessions are audio and videorecorded (after participants have signed an informed consent form) and are usable for the audio and visual dissemination. Participants can choose to make available to the video-dissemination only some fragments from their video interviews conducted by the researcher. Furthermore, participants have a third option: a voluntary non-professional actor can videorecord the excerpts from the interview, lending his/her face for the recording. A detailed informed consent form concerning the dissemination is submitted to the participants and images, and voices are masked when the participants request it.

The research is hybrid in its use of visuals: 1) Each mother collects pictures of her everyday life with the EthnoAlly³ app (Favero & Theunissen, 2018) on her mobile phone. These pictures are interpreted by the researcher, but they are also discussed in the photovoice session with mothers as participants and in the focus groups with judicial system professionals. Hence, visuals are used *as data* and *as tools to gather data* by photo-elicitation and by the focus groups. 2) Then, they are used *as tools to disseminate findings*. Indeed, visual fragments from the videorecording of the interviews, from the photovoice, from the focus groups, and pictures collected by the mothers are utilized for the visual dissemination of the findings. The visual dissemination is structured into short videos produced by the researcher (with her explanations, image and voice) which include video excerpts from the interviews with the participants, pictures collected by the mothers, and video excerpts from the photovoice sessions and the focus groups. In addition,

videos provide an explanation of the maps created during the research fieldwork. Maps are a typical tool of IE, and showing and commenting on them can improve people's understandings of some processes. Maps are graphic objects that can be shown through digital animations with specific software, enhancing the understanding of abstract aspects of practices or social processes.

In this ongoing study, the visual dissemination aims to reach an academic public, a non-academic public (such as policy makers, stakeholders, professionals) and a broader general public. Videos and pictures are shared through different platforms like a dedicated channel on YouTube, a website, Twitter and Facebook. This kind of dissemination is intended to explain, through the visual materials from the research fieldwork, the standpoint of the single mothers in different countries and the invisible and taken-for-granted forms of governance that rule their everyday lives. In this study, the choice of investing energies and time in a visual video dissemination has the purpose of impacting on a broader non-academic public, sensitizing policy makers, professionals and citizens to single mothers' problems.

A second example is provided by an IE study conducted by Puddu (2018) that used visuals *as data* and *as tools to disseminate findings*. Puddu's study explored how vulnerable youths' lives are socially organized during urban revitalization in Edmonton, Canada. This community-based participatory research project utilized participant observation, field notes, open-ended interviews, focus groups and photovoice. Using the photovoice method, Puddu asked street-involved youths to collect photographs about how urban revitalization shaped their experiences in order to gain better understanding of their daily lives and their perspectives on the impact of the fast growing district. Outputs of the photovoice study were a photographic booklet and a public exhibit by means of which the youths concerned were able to present their photographs and stories to

citizens, stakeholders and local authorities. In the booklet, pictures taken by the participants were accompanied by fragments from the interviews and author's comments. These outputs made it possible to connect youth with policy makers and the community.

In conclusion, following the considerations of Herzog (2020) about the intertwining of visual methods and social problems research, it is possible to argue that the two research studies presented above mainly aim to use visuals to direct the *public audience's attention to social problems*.

An Open-Ended Conclusion

This paper has illustrated some aspects of visual methods and their intertwining with IE. Then, by illustrating various studies, it has shown how researchers can utilize visual materials as data, as tools to gather data, as tools to record data, and as tools to disseminate findings. This conclusion summarizes the intertwining between visual research methods and IE and the possibilities that it offers to social problems research, highlighting its strengths and weaknesses.

A first strength concerns the *adaptability* of visuals and visual methods to the IE approach.

Visual materials and different visual methods can be brought into an IE project and adapted to its specific theoretical and methodological characteristics. The study by Luken and Vaughan (2006) provides an example of this adaptability using visual data as second-level data in IE (see also Campbell & Gregor, 2002), which are data collected outside or beyond people's experiential accounts. In the aforementioned study, these visual data enable explanation of the linkages among local accounts, local actions and social relations of ruling, and they reinforce the explanation and the interpretation of those processes. Furthermore, the study by McCoy (1995) provides an example of how photo-elicitation can be adapted to the IE approach, as the

researcher organizes a small group to discuss the interpretive processes of the activation of the bride's pictures.

On the other hand, IE shows *flexibility* by including visual research methods but retaining its own methodological and theoretical characteristics, as in the study on court-appointed experts' practices (Tartari, 2018). In other words, an IE project can flexibly integrate visuals as data and as tools to gather, to record and to disseminate data. Since the IE approach is a sociology in itself (DeVault, 2020), fruitful integrations and exchanges are possible in relation to visual methods. Furthermore, one of the most important strengths seems to be the link among the *materiality* of visuals, the focus of IE on materiality itself, and the *sensitivity* of IE to people, their standpoints, their everyday experiences, and the concrete aspects of discursive and cultural representations. The utilization of visuals and visual methods, which help to maintain the focus on the real social world and its materiality, enhances this kind of IE sensitivity. For example, in the study on court-appointed experts (Tartari, 2018), it is precisely the materiality of the visual text that enables participants to keep the focus on their actual practices, describing and discussing them in detail. Bringing the materiality of visual texts into IE also makes it possible to achieve greater *richness* in narrating experiences (Rose, 2012). For example, in the study on court-appointed experts, the visual texts used for the photo-elicitation were able to generate processes of identification and differentiation by the experts that would not be activated in the same way by a verbal question of the researcher. The materiality of visual texts enables participants to explain aspects of the social world that could be difficult to express or show verbally; then, they enable researchers to grasp these aspects. An example of this process of *overcoming verbal limits* can be found in the study by Puddu (2019) where, through pictures collected by the participants, a stigmatized condition

like youth homelessness can be analyzed, displayed and communicated by the participants and the researcher.

Puddu's study affords explanation of another strength of involving visuals in the research process: *equalizing power*. Visuals enable a horizontal approach to be taken between interviewer and interviewees, reducing power inequalities. Therefore, visuals are recommended when researchers are in situations where the power between them and the participants is particularly unequal, for instance research with children (e.g., Mannay, 2010), with immigrants, or with disadvantaged groups, like the vulnerable youth in Puddu's work. Indeed, visuals become an excellent instrument when researchers study intersections and use the intersectionality approach. Therefore, when there are power inequalities in the relation between the researcher and the participants and/or when participants come from life experiences of inequality and stigma, visual methods can facilitate the dialogue between researcher and participants, both when visuals are used as tools to gather data and when they are used to record them.

Finally, implementing visual methods in IE improves *effective action to disseminate research results and involve* stakeholders and policy makers. Firstly, these methods allow communication with participants and different audiences using means that are meaningful to them, as Herzog (2020) suggests. In a society that uses visual representation as a primary form of communication, visual research methods and visual disseminations (like, for example, short videos, booklets with photographs, photographic exhibitions) are important tools. An example of dissemination practices of this kind can be found in my study on single mothers and judicial system (Tartari, 2019). Furthermore, mapping – a typical tool of IE – can be displayed in videos with animations in order to explain social processes to a non-academic public. Visual dissemination can be done through social media platforms (like Youtube, Facebook, and Twitter) and it can reach different

audiences and sensitize them, achieving one of the main aims of IE. This kind of dissemination does not replace the traditional form of written dissemination through academic journals, but it can constitute a parallel channel.

Visual research methods and visual practices of results dissemination can be properly included in IE studies, strengthening the social mission of IE as a sociology for people. In regard to the social mission of IE, to be considered is what Vannini (2019) states about public ethnography and visuals: “In our digital age, multimodality is not an option for ethnography but a necessity” (p, 4). Vannini explains that a multimodal message concerns not a single mode of communication, but more than one. In other words, (academic) writing is not enough to reach a wider audience. Researchers need to use other modes of communication and to learn other effective strategies for communicating, following the examples of other disciplines like human geography and anthropology. Vannini underlines the potential of ethnographers in developing visual disseminations: they are sensitive and able to involve themselves directly in the life world of participants and to interpret these experiences, describing and explaining such interpretation to different audiences. Even if Vannini considers other kinds of ethnography, his suggestions can be usefully applied to IE. Concluding, the use of visuals, in many of the forms analyzed in this paper, contributes *to giving voice to the participants*, who are often without voice, as in the studies by Puddu (2018) and Tartari (2019). If Van den Scott (2018) suggests that visuals are a form of answer, I argue that the use of visuals in IE as tools to disseminate findings consists, above all, in questions and answers that can generate forms of dialogic reflexivity in dealing with social problems.

The use of visuals in IE as data, as research methods, and as tools for dissemination has also some potential weaknesses. The first of them concerns *how to define visual texts as appropriate*

for use in an IE. Replicability and “incorporation” are the necessary characteristics of such texts, as explained by Smith and Turner (2014). It follows that a critical analysis should be conducted on visual texts to ensure that they are suitable for use or interpretation. Analyzing visuals as data and/or selecting them as tools requires practice, critical thinking and a good theoretical knowledge of IE. As in other kinds of ethnographies, researchers should manage visual data like textual data: internal patterns and/or links to the external data should be sought. This search should be systematic and reflexive (Van den Scott, 2018). The study by Luken and Vaughan (2006) provides a good example of visual data that are effective in showing how discourses affect social practices. The authors made an extensive collection of materials like brochures from different sources assuring the quality of historical archival data that they analyzed, and then linked them to the interviews that they conducted.

However, the problem of the appropriateness of visual texts concerns mainly the situation when visuals are tools for gathering data, as in photo-elicitation. A visual text used for photo-elicitation should be selected with attention to its replicability and incorporation in the actual settings of people’s everyday lives. For instance, in the study on court-appointed experts, the selection and creation of images that represented recurrent situations in work processes needed critical attention to my personal and professional practices of looking, because that “looking” could generate biases in selecting the images. The way in which researchers “look” is socially organized; it is not a neutral practice. Furthermore, visuals are embedded in social settings and situations, and their uses can be culture-sensitive, age-sensitive, gender-sensitive and generation-sensitive. For this reason, critical attention is necessary to determine when and how the selection of images can be biased.

Another important weakness of the intertwining of IE with visual methods concerns the *ethics*. The more the aim is to give voice to the participants and make ethnography *public* through the use of visual materials, the more the use of visuals in research and dissemination requires careful consideration of ethical issues. Pictures and videos of the participants (collected by the researcher or by themselves) can be shown to a small group (for example in a focus group or in a photovoice session), but also to a wide public audience. Some ways of preventing rejections by ethical committees regarding showing images and videos for the dissemination include: 1) the preparation of a detailed information sheet and consent form to protect participants and researchers by stating clearly the use of the images before, during, and after the research study and how they will be manipulated; 2) the application of audio and visual masking (i.e., the masking of faces, bodies and voices) in videorecordings, pictures or podcasts that will be used to disseminate findings; 3) the utilization of semi-fictional methods involving volunteers as non-professional actors (an actor who lends his/her face and voice to the participant), as in the study on single mothers and judicial system (Tartari, 2019).

It is useful to conclude by highlighting that other strengths and weaknesses can be found in the theoretical and methodological intertwining between IE and visual methods. Therefore, the discussion remains open.

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Endnotes

¹ This IE project is a self-funded research study, carried out by myself in collaboration with the University of Padua for the recruitment of the subjects and the conduct of the study. Regarding ethical issues, the study complies with the code of conduct elaborated by AIS - Associazione Italiana di Sociologia, and meets international legal and ethics requirements.

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³ EthnoAlly is a mobile application that enables researchers to create and organize multimodal field notes for ethnographic studies. It can be downloaded for free on smartphones – by iOS and Android – and it produces GNSS-tagged multimodal material that can be archived, organized and analyzed on a cloud application server. EthnoAlly is a research tool designed specifically for the purpose of helping anthropologists and other social scientists conducting sensory, participatory, and multimodal ethnographic research. EthnoAlly is also a participatory research tool. Participants can download the app onto their smartphones and generate images, text notes, sound files and geolocate and temporal metadata to share with the researcher. In this way, the app can work as an extension of the ethnographer’s fieldwork.